

Radiographical and histopathological changes of silver nanoparticles on induced periodontitis in rats

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Abstract

Periodontal Pocket provides an ideal environment for the growth and proliferation of anaerobic pathogenic bacteria in order to complement non-surgical therapy in periodontitis, there are multiple options of antimicrobials, such as metronidazole, chlorhexidine, minocycline, doxycycline and tetracycline, which can be locally delivered into the mucosa. These drugs are used in periodontal pockets and can inhibit or eliminate periodontopathogenic microorganisms as well as modulate the inflammatory response of tissues. Numerous metal nanoparticles, such as magnesium, gold, silver and others, were studied for application as antimicrobial agents, however AgNPs have proved to be the most effective against a broad spectrum of microorganisms. It is widely known that silver free molecule has strong antimicrobial potential. Therefore, AgNPs can be used in medicine for burn treatment, dental materials, water treatment, lotions.

Keywords:

Minocycline, Experimental periodontitis, Nano-silver, Albino rat.

Introduction

Periodontitis describes a group of related inflammatory disease resulting in destruction of the tissues that support the tooth. It results from extension of the inflammatory process initiated in the gingiva to the supporting periodontal tissues. Due to the fact that periodontitis is caused by bacteria, the most important line of treatment is elimination of these bacteria. Therapeutic approach for periodontitis concerning elimination of bacteria, either with hand instrumentation or with electronic instrumentation along with use of chemotherapeutic agents, systemically or locally. The systemic antibiotic therapy has various disadvantages like, hypersensitivity reactions, organ toxicity and development of resistant bacteria. Topical administration of antibacterial agents in the form of mouth washes, dentifrices or gel are effective measures in controlling supragingival plaque. The present

study aimed to compare the efficacy of 2% minocycline and 25 microgram per milliliter($\mu\text{g/ml}$) Nano-silver gel, locally applied to induced periodontitis in rats, radiographical and histopathological result

Methods

One hundred and ten male albino rats were included. Group I (healthy or negative control group): consisted of 10 healthy rats without induction of experimental periodontitis (animals neither subjected to experimentally- induced periodontitis nor treated).After induction of experimental periodontitis (EPD) using elastic ring, rats were randomly divided into the following experimental groups; group II (positive control group): consisted of 40 rats with experimentally- induced periodontitis (infected but not treated, group III (Nano-silver group): consisted of 30 rats, animals subjected to EPD and treated with 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ gel once daily,

group IV(minocycline group): consisted of 30 rats, animals subjected to EPD and treated with 2% minocycline once daily. Baseline assessment was conducted on day 0 (before drug treatment). Evaluation of the inflammation during drug

treatment was conducted on days 7, 15 and 30). Ten rats from each group were sacrificed at each time point (7, 15 and 30 days) for radiographic and histopathological assessment.

Scores used for histopathological analysis.

Score	Criteria
0	From 0 to < 5 inflammatory cellular infiltration restricted to the region of the marginal gingiva, with preserved alveolar process.
1	Moderate cellular infiltration, from 5 to< 15 (all over the attached gingiva) with superficial alveolar bone resorption.
2	Intense cellular infiltration, from 15 to< 30, with evident alveolar bone resorption.
3	Severe cellular infiltrate, more than 30, and complete resorption of the alveolar process.

Radiographic imaging:

maxillae were placed at 10 cm from the x-ray tube. Periapical radiographic films (size 1) were used to accommodate anterior maxillary area of rats.

The maxillae were placed over the film and fixed by wax, parallel to floor, and towards the exposure side. Vertical angulation of x ray tube was approximately +45-55 degree and horizontal angulation (0 degrees) and central ray oriented toward the middle of film (bisecting angle technique) with K.V.P 10 ma, and 0.24 seconds exposure time. The films were developed automatically to minimize the projection geometrical errors.

Results

Nano-silver gel showed a superior antibacterial effect compared to minocycline gel in terms of improvement in radiographic result as well as histopathological findings regarding significant reduction in the inflammatory cell count and bone showing significant regenerations.

Discussion

A study used Nano-silver -based bone grafts combined with bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP-2) had successfully resulted in bone regeneration, in an in vivo study, in a rat femoral

segmental defect (FSD) infected with *Staph. aureus* and *MRSA* strain. Liu et al. (2012) used Nano-silver coated with stainless alloy in a rat femoral canal model, to test the antibacterial and osteoconductive properties of Nano-silver. They found that Nano-silver particles coated with stainless steel alloy implants had significantly induced bone regeneration despite bacterial contamination. Zhang R et al. used Nano-silver encapsulated with collagen, in treatment of mouse femoral fracture model. They found that Nano-silver promoted the formation of fracture callus and induced early closure of the fracture gap. Their results depend on a speculation that Nano-silver may promote chemo-attraction of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) and fibroblasts to migrate to the fracture site.

Conclusion

Nano-silver gel in the used shape, size, concentration and route of administration, as well as follow-up period, was efficient as a local treatment of periodontitis in rats. Nano-silver gel at a concentration of 25 µg/ml had superior antibacterial effect than 2% minocycline gel in treating experimentally- induced periodontitis in rats. Results showed improved histopathologic changes and bone density enhancement.

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